

Snell's Law and X, T Independence in the Classical Action Part II

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In Part I (1) we argued that in a Snell law situation the horizontal distances of the angled light beams in n_1 and n_2 media should be the same ratio as $v_1 T$ and $v_2 T$. For equal angled distances of L , one then obtains Snell's law. We argued that this arises for the horizontal component if one considers the time part of the action $A = -Et + px$ and imposes $E T = E T$. In such a case one has $d_1 = v_1 T$ and $d_2 = v_2 T$ which one insists have the same ratio as $L/v_1 \sin(\theta_1)$ and $L/v_2 \sin(\theta_2)$.

In this note we wish to emphasize that the horizontal component, parallel to the interface of the two media is also linked to:

$p_1 \text{ parallel} = p_2 \text{ parallel}$ (2) so both E and energy flow are the same for this component.

Secondly, we wish to examine how this approach is linked to Fermat's principle which "minimizes time of travel".

Recap of Argument from Part I

In part 1 we argued that the classical action $A = -Et + px$ treats t and x as independent. If light were moving in one medium, with a refractive index of n_1 , which has the same E and p then the time portion of the classical action would be: $E T$. This also means that the phase is $\exp(-iET)$.

If light were moving in medium with n_2 then for a constant time portion of A one would also have $E T$ and the same phase $\exp(-iET)$. Speeds in the two media are different, however, namely: $w/c (1/n_1)$ and $w/c (1/n_2)$ where c is the speed of light and w the angular frequency. Thus the distances traveled in the two media are:

$$d_1 = (w/c) (1/n_1) T \quad \text{and} \quad d_2 = (w/c) (1/n_2) T \quad ((1))$$

For a Snell's law scenario in which a beam of angled light making an angle θ_1 with the normal moves into a second medium (with a horizontal line representing the boundary of the two media), then the beam will bend such that an angle θ_2 is made with the normal. Taking equal lengths L for each beam, we argue that the horizontal component of distance:

$d_1 = L \sin(\theta_1)$ and $d_2 = L \sin(\theta_2)$ have the same ratio as in ((1)). This leads directly to Snell's law:

$$\sin(\theta_1) / \sin(\theta_2) = n_2 / n_1 \quad ((2))$$

In Part I we did not emphasize why the horizontal component of distance is chosen. We argue here that it is because $p_1 \text{ horizontal} = p_2 \text{ horizontal}$ (2). In fact (as shown in (2)) one may derive Snell's law directly from this equation with $p_i \text{ horizontal} = n_i (w/c) \sin(\theta_i)$. Here we wish to consider the idea of action such that the particle does not distinguish that it is moving in one medium or another with respect to the time part of the action $A = -Et + px$ which treats t and x as independent i.e. the phase $\exp(-iET)$ is the same for such a scenario. We note that for the actual angled light beam time is not the same for the horizontal components i.e. one has L/v_1 and

L/v_2 . We create the equal time scenario to find the ratio of d_1/d_2 based on action arguments and then apply this ratio to an actual experimental angled light situation. One needs to have both E and p the same for this approach to work it seems and so it is only the horizontal component which leads to $ET = ET$ as discussed above. The same L is used as the horizontal distance sweeps out this L as if it were fixed at the top end.

Thus the main argument we make is that: $d_1/d_2 = n_2/n_1$. ((3))

Fermat's Principle

As shown in (2) Fermat's principle involves choosing a starting point for an angled beam in medium n_1 that is a distance of "a" above the horizontal media interface. This beam hits the horizontal at some unknown point x from a point directly below "a" called "O". In the medium the beam bends and passes through a point "b" below the horizontal and $l-x$ from "O" where l is a constant. If one writes the time traveled by each straight line beam i.e.

$$\text{Hypotenuse}_1 / v_1 + \text{hypotenuse}_2 / v_2 = \text{overall time} \quad ((4))$$

Both hypotenuses may be written as functions of x and one may take d/dx of ((4)) setting it equal to 0 (high minimizing) to find Snell's law.

We argue that this is a somewhat unusual approach in that if one knows the momentum (magnitude and direction) of the beam in n_1 one knows exactly at which point it hits the media interface. What is unknown is how it will bend (if one does not know Snell's law). Fermat's principle takes an opposite approach considering different initial momentum in n_1 and bent rays in medium n_2 which pass through a point b below the horizontal and $l-x$ from "O" where l is a constant. Fermat's approach seems to give the impression that a beam starting in n_1 anticipates the full trip through n_1 and n_2 and executes it in order to minimize time. In fact, a beam in n_1 with a given momentum vector travels to the interface as if there were no medium n_2 . Thus we seek an alternative argument to the minimization of time even though mathematically this produces Snell's law.

Our starting point is ((3)) $d_1/d_2 = n_2/n_1$ where d_1 and d_2 are the horizontal components of the beams in both media and $L_1=L_2=L$ for beam length. We argue that this is the main principle involved. These distances are x and $l-x$ in Fermat's problems. Mathematically the hypotenuse is linked to the horizontal distance in such a case i.e.

$$d/dx \text{ hypotenuse}_1 = d/dx \sqrt{aa + xx} = x / \sqrt{aa+xx} = \sin(\theta_1) \quad ((5a))$$

$$d/dx \text{ hypotenuse}_2 = d/dx \sqrt{bb + (l-x)(l-x)} = (l-x) / \sqrt{bb + (l-x)(l-x)} \quad ((5b))$$

If $L = \text{hypotenuse}_1 = \text{hypotenuse}_2$ then d_1/d_2 is mathematically equivalent to $d/dx \text{ hypotenuse}_1 / d/dx \text{ hypotenuse}_2$. Using this in ((3)) yields:

$$d/dx \text{ hypotenuse}_1 = (n_2/n_1) d/dx \text{ hypotenuse}_2 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is of the form of a minimization problem, but it is really based on ((3)) and a mathematical property of the expression for the hypotenuse of a right angle triangle. Thus it is not necessarily the case that the beam somehow knows that it must minimize time. There may be other ways of viewing the situation such as considering a constant time portion of the action $-Et + px$ if E and p are the same in each medium. In such a case, one considers equal T motion in both although this forces distances to be different i.e. creates d_1 and d_2 . This ratio is then applied to an actual angled light beam bending scenario. $\exp(-iET)$ is a kind of cycling scenario which is the same in each medium, but with different distances d_1 and d_2 .

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that to insist that the time portion of the classical action $-Et + px$ namely $-Et$ remain constant, one needs E and p constant in each medium. In such a case one may argue that $ET = ET$ in each medium. This means that the distances traveled $d_1 = v_1 T$ and $d_2 = v_2 T$ are different because $v_1/v_2 = n_2/n_1$. For an angled beam moving from n_1 into n_2 we use L as representing both hypotenuses and argue that d_1 and d_2 the horizontal components keep the same ratio $d_1/d_2 = n_2/n_1$ because $p_1 \text{ parallel} = p_2 \text{ parallel}$. We argue that the ratio d_1/d_2 remains the same in the angled scenario because d_1 and d_2 are associated with the same energy flow $p_1 \text{ parallel} = p_2 \text{ parallel}$.

We compare this approach to Fermat's minimum time one and argue that d_1 and d_2 may be written as x and $l-x$ and that the formula for the hypotenuse (Pythagoreas theorem) is of the form that $d/dx \text{ hypotenuse} = x/L$ or $(x-l)/L$ for $L_1=L_2=L$. Thus d_1/d_2 may be written in terms of derivatives of hypotenuses and $d_1/d_2 = n_2/n_1$ has the form: $d/dx F(x) = 0$ which is the same as a minimization equation. As a result, the minimization of time may be more of a mathematical result than a physical one in terms of actual motion of a light beam. We argue this because given a momentum vector in medium 1 one knows that light will behave as if there were no medium until it reaches the medium interface. Within the medium it should also move in a straight line, it is just that the angles are different.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)